

1 Gold nanoparticles functionalized by rhodamine B 2 isothiocyanate: a new tool to control plasmonic 3 effects

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21

1 **Abstract**

2 Gold nanoparticles with an average diameter of 10 nm, functionalized by the dye molecule
3 rhodamine B isothiocyanate, have been synthesized. The resulting material has been extensively
4 characterized both chemically, to investigate the bonding between the dye molecules and the
5 nanoparticles, and physically, to understand the details of the aggregation induced by interaction
6 between dye molecules on different nanoparticles. The plasmonic response of the system has
7 been further characterized by measurement and theoretical simulation of the static UV-Vis
8 extinction spectra of the aggregates produced following different synthesis procedures. The model
9 parameters used in the simulation gave further useful information on the aggregation and its
10 relationship to the plasmonic response. Finally, we investigated the time dependence of the
11 plasmonic effects of the nanoparticles and fluorescence of the dye molecule using an ultrafast
12 pump-probe optical method. By modulating the quantity of dye molecules on the surface of the
13 nanoparticles it was possible to exert fine control over the plasmonic response of nanoparticles.

14 **Keywords:** gold nanoparticles; rhodamine B; plasmonic nanoparticles; transient spectroscopy.

15

16 **1. Introduction**

17 Noble metal nanoparticles (NPs) exhibit many fascinating optical,¹ magnetic,² thermal,³ and
18 electrical⁴ properties, which are widely exploited for applications in different fields, such as
19 optoelectronics,^{5,6} catalysis,^{7,8} sensors,^{9,10,11} and biomedicine.^{12,13,14} Many of these
20 applications are based on the NPs' remarkable property of strongly enhancing the local
21 electromagnetic near-field.¹⁵ Together with the effect of the Localized Surface Plasmon
22 Resonance (LSPR), this can lead to extremely strong light absorption and scattering by the

1 NPs, *e.g.* their absorption cross sections are up to 5-6 orders of magnitude higher than the
2 most strongly absorbing organic dye molecules.¹⁶ This has led to the use of NPs as beacons
3 to enhance processes in nearby molecules.^{17,18} Controlling the plasmonic response of NPs
4 and metal nanostructures is the first step in exploiting the features of the plasmon
5 resonance that are central to many of the above mentioned applications.^{19,20,21} Various
6 routes have been employed in the literature to achieve this goal with the principal ones
7 being the control over the material, size and shape of the NPs.^{22,23} This has led to the
8 synthesis of a plethora of shapes of Au and Ag NPs such as rods, prisms, stars, cages, core
9 shells and more, with plasmonic responses ranging from the visible to the IR.^{24,25} It is also
10 possible to control the plasmonic response of a nanostructure by exploiting the coupling of
11 plasmonic resonances between closely spaced NPs.^{26,27} The coupling, which can be
12 described in terms of a hybridization model, leads to strong changes in the frequency of
13 the LSPR. In the case of a 1D/linear 'chain' of closely spaced NPs the plasmon resonance
14 undergoes a blue shift when the polarization of the electromagnetic field is perpendicular
15 to the inter-axis of the chain (transverse plasmon). On the other hand, a red shifted SPR
16 arises when the polarization is aligned along the inter-axis (extended plasmon).^{28,29} The
17 plasmonic shift of the extended plasmon is related to the ratio of the gap between the NPs
18 to the particle diameter. The small gap sizes required for plasmon control can be achieved
19 via top down methods only for large particles (>100 nm) while chemical methods are
20 typically required when nanometer control is needed, as in the case of small particles (<20
21 nm).³⁰ Extremely precise control has been gained over the gaps between NPs by means of
22 chemical synthesis and the use of linker molecules which can be carefully tailored to
23 change the gap size.^{31,30} Another interesting approach consists in the combination of
24 chemical synthesis with self-assembly on surfaces which has led to plasmonic structures

1 with resonances in the near IR.^{32,33} Induced aggregation of NPs has been known to change
2 the plasmonic response of NPs for a long time and has even been used as the basis of an
3 assay method of DNA. In fact, the addition of the target DNA to suitably functionalized NPs
4 causes a plasmon shift whose size can be used to measure the added quantity of DNA.^{34,35}
5 In this work, we focus on the synthesis of gold nanoparticles, with diameters around 10
6 nm, functionalized by rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RITC). The resulting nanostructures
7 have been extensively characterized in order to understand both the chemical structure
8 (molecule-particle interaction) and the aggregation properties (particle-particle
9 interaction). The chemical structure has been investigated using Fourier Transform
10 InfraRed (FTIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and X-ray Photoelectron (XPS)
11 spectroscopies to establish the bonding of the capping molecules with the NPs, while the
12 physical characteristics were monitored by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Field-
13 Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) to gain insight into the shape and size of
14 NPs.

15 Furthermore, we have used both theoretical and experimental methods to investigate the
16 static UV-Vis extinction spectra of the systems. The comparison of the simulated spectra to
17 the experiment has allowed the interparticle distance in the aggregates to be evaluated.
18 Finally, we investigated the time dependence of the plasmonic effects of the NPs and
19 fluorescence of the dye molecule using an ultrafast pump-probe optical method. The
20 overlap of the dye emission with the LSPR means that the fluorescence of molecules in
21 close proximity to the surface of the NPs are efficiently quenched. The time resolved
22 spectroscopy permits us to distinguish between fluorescence of the dye molecules in
23 solution and the plasmonic response of NPs.

1 The multi characterization approach employed has allowed us to understand the link
2 between chemical structure, aggregation due to particle-particle interactions and their
3 effects on the plasmonic response. This understanding permits the modulation of the
4 experimental parameters to tune the properties of the aggregates and thus optimise the
5 applicative perspectives, opening new opportunities in the field of optical materials.

6

7 **2. Materials and methods**

8 *2.1 Synthesis and purification of Au@RITC NPs*

9 The synthesis procedure is similar to that reported in our previous works³⁶ and has been
10 performed using different metal precursor/RITC molar ratios, (Au/RITC= 1/4, 1/2, 1/1 and
11 1/0.1, see also Supporting Information, Table S1a). In a typical procedure, for example
12 Au/RITC=1/1 (mol/mol) (Au@RITC_1), a water solution of RITC (0.265 g, 5.078×10^{-4} mol, in
13 the 10 mL of deionized water) is mixed with a water solution of the gold precursor (0.200 g
14 HAuCl_4 , 5.078×10^{-4} mol, in the 10 mL of deionized water), and the solution was bubbled
15 under nitrogen at room temperature for 10 min. Subsequently, 0.096 g of NaBH_4 ($2.538 \times$
16 10^{-3} mol) dissolved in 10 mL of deionized water were added. The mixture reacts for 2 h at
17 room temperature, under magnetic stirring. The product obtained has been separated by
18 centrifugation with 10 mL of deionized water, at 13,000 rpm, 20 min, 3 times (step 1,
19 sample Au@RITC_1a), 10 times (step 2, sample Au@RITC_1b) or 20 times + washing in
20 CHCl_3 (step 3, sample Au@RITC_1c). Au/RITC=1/0.1 yield (after step 2): 15 ± 2 % (wt);
21 Au/RITC=1/1 yield (after step 2): 25 ± 3 % (wt).

22 The main parameters of the characterizations for the Au@RITC_1b sample are (for others
23 samples see Supporting Information, Table S1b):

1 UV-Vis (in H₂O), λ_{\max} (nm): 612 nm; FT-IR (film CH₂Cl₂), ν (cm⁻¹): $\nu_{\text{C=O}} = 1717$; $\delta_{\text{CH}_2} 1395$ DLS
2 in H₂O, $\langle 2R_H \rangle$ (nm): 10 ± 3 nm; ζ potential in H₂O, [mV]: -28 ± 3 mV.

3

4 *2.2 Characterization of Au@RITC NPs*

5 UV-Vis spectra were recorded in aqueous solution by using quartz cells with a Varian Cary
6 100 Scan spectrophotometer. FTIR spectra were carried out in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ range,
7 using a Bruker Vertex 70 instrument and a KRS-5 cell; the samples were prepared as drop
8 casted films.

9 The sizes and size distributions of Au@RITC in aqueous solution were investigated using
10 the dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique using a Zetasizer instrument (Malvern) at a
11 temperature of $25.0 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ and concentration 0.02 mg/mL. Correlation data were
12 acquired and fitted in analogy to our previous work.^{37,38}

13 The ζ potential of gold nanoparticles was measured by means of the laser
14 microelectrophoresis technique in a thermostated cell ($T = 25.0 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$).³⁹

15 NMR spectra were carried out by using a Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer operating at a
16 frequency of 400.13 MHz for the proton. The compounds were suspended in 0.6 ml of
17 deuterium oxide with 3-(Trimethylsilyl)propionic-2,2,3,3-d₄ acid sodium salt (TSP) at a
18 concentration of 2 mM as a chemical shift and concentration reference. Bidimensional ¹H
19 homonuclear NOESY experiments were acquired with a mixing time of 150 ms at 298 K, a
20 spectral width of 15 ppm in both dimensions employing a matrix of 4k x 256 data points, a
21 repetition time of 2 s and 16 scans.⁴⁰

22 FESEM images were obtained using a Zeiss Auriga 405, adopting a voltage level of 7.5 keV
23 and a working distance of 2.5 mm, on freshly prepared films, drop casted from deionized
24 water solutions directly on the metallic sample holder.

1 Synchrotron radiation XPS experiments were carried out at the BACH (Beam line for
2 Advanced DiCHroism) beam line at the ELETTRA synchrotron facility of Trieste (Italy). The
3 BACH beam line exploits the intense radiation emitted from an undulator front-end. XPS
4 data were collected in the fixed analyzer transmission mode (pass energy = 30 eV), with the
5 monochromator entrance and exit slits fixed at 30 μm . A photon energy of 380 eV was
6 used for the C1s, S2p and Au4f spectral regions, while 596 eV was used for the N1s and O1s
7 spectral regions, both with a photon energy resolution of 0.22 eV. Calibration of the energy
8 scale was made by referencing all of the spectra to the Fermi edge of an Au reference
9 sample, and the Au4f_{7/2}, was always found at 83.96 eV. Curve-fitting analysis of the C1s,
10 S2p, N1s, O1s, Au4f spectra was performed using Gaussian curves as fitting functions.
11 S2p_{3/2,1/2} and Au4f_{7/2,5/2} doublets were fitted by using the same Full Width at Half-
12 Maximum (FWHM) for each pair of components of the same core level, a spin-orbit
13 splitting of, respectively, 1.2 eV and 3.7 eV and branching ratios S2p_{3/2}/S2p_{1/2} = 2/1,
14 Au4f_{7/2}/Au4f_{5/2} = 4/3. When several different species were identified in a spectrum, the
15 same FWHM value was used for all individual photoemission bands. The samples were
16 drop casted onto TiO₂/Si(111) wafers surfaces from water solutions (c = 1 mg/mL).

17 ~~2.3 Transient Absorption Spectroscopy~~

18 The pump-probe experiments were performed using a laser system consisting of a 1 kHz, 4
19 mJ, 35 fs chirped pulse amplifier seeded by a Ti:Sa oscillator. The pump pulse (400 nm) was
20 generated by frequency doubling of the fundamental light (800 nm) while the probe was
21 generated by taking a small quantity of 800 nm light (3 μJ) and focusing it into a rotating
22 CaF₂ crystal. The optical layout of the commercial transient absorption spectrometer
23 (FemtoFrame II, IB Photonics) consists of a split beam configuration in which 50 % of the
24 white light (350 - 800 nm) passes through the sample contained in a 1 mm static cell while

1 the remainder is used as a reference to account for pulse to pulse fluctuations in the white
2 light generation. The pump pulse is loosely focused (circular spot of $d = 700 \mu\text{m}$) onto the
3 sample with a power density of $150 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. The probe pulse is much smaller (approx. 150
4 μm) and is scanned in time by varying the length of its optical path.

5

6 *2.3 Theoretical methods*

7 The present simulations are based on the Finite Integration Technique (FIT). It is a powerful
8 numerical approach for solving electromagnetic problems, especially suitable for large
9 dimension structures with detailed features. It was first introduced by Thomas Weiland in
10 1977.⁴¹ It is based on the solution of the Maxwell equations in their integral form. This
11 approach allows the division of the overall simulation domain into smaller portions (units)
12 with each of them being separately solved. Continuity relations among adjacent units
13 provide the consistency of the general electromagnetic solution. Naturally, the mesh
14 chosen for FIT simulations is crucial to achieve correct results. In the present case, we have
15 adopted a tetrahedral mesh, which is especially suitable for curved surfaces. The FIT
16 method allows the calculation in both near- and far-field; hence quantities such as electric-
17 field distributions or extinction spectra can be efficiently determined by this numerical
18 technique. The wavelength dependent theoretical dielectric function of RITC was
19 constructed starting from its absorbance profile combined with a Drude-Lorentz
20 formalism.^{42,3}

21 Finally, in the present study, the convergence analysis approach has been especially
22 stressed, due to the strongly irregular morphology of the structure of the NP chains in
23 comparison to, for example, individual spherical particles. In this way, the error drops
24 below 1% for the far-field results.

1 **3. Results and discussions**

2 *3.1 Au@RITC NPs synthesis and characterizations*

3 The aim of this work is to directly link an organic dye to the gold nanoparticle (AuNPs)
4 surface: RITC has been chosen as a capping agent during the gold nanoparticle synthesis to
5 obtain dye-AuNPs direct functionalization and to optimize the proximity between the dye
6 and AuNPs. The RITC functionalized AuNPs were prepared by reduction in a single water
7 phase starting from the metal precursor in the presence of the dye, as schematically
8 reported in Fig. 1 (details in Supporting Information Table S1a).

9 The synthesis was initially conducted with ~~two~~ different molar ratios between the metal
10 and the capping agent, *i.e.* molar ratio 1/1 (sample Au@RITC_1), ~~and~~ molar ratio 1/0.1
11 (sample Au@RITC_2), molar ratio 1/2 (sample Au@RITC_3) and molar ratio 1/4 (sample
12 Au@RITC_4). This has allowed us to identify the Au@RITC_1 as being produced in the best
13 synthetic conditions, both in terms of yields, and especially in terms of dimension and
14 dispersity.

15 As shown in Fig. 2a, for Au/RITC = 1/1 (mol/mol) (sample Au@RITC_1) we obtained mean
16 particle size of 10 ± 3 nm and yield of 25% (wt) while for the Au/RITC = 1/0.1 molar ratio
17 (sample Au@RITC_2) the particles obtained are polydispersed, showing two different size
18 populations at 50 ± 20 nm, and 500 ± 30 nm, with a yield of 15% (wt). As reported in the
19 Supporting Information, Table S1b, for Au/RITC = 1/2 (mol/mol) (sample Au@RITC_3) and
20 Au/RITC = 1/4 (mol/mol) (sample Au@RITC_4) we obtained strongly irregular and
21 polydispersed samples of NPs. For these reasons, it was decided to use only the 1/1 molar
22 ratio sample.

3 **Fig. 1** General synthetic scheme of Au@RITC nanoparticles.

4 A careful and controlled purification was performed on Au@RITC₁ to modulate the dye
 5 concentration on the surface of the nanoparticles. Three different samples have been
 6 selected, *i.e.* Au@RITC_{1a}, Au@RITC_{1b} and Au@RITC_{1c}, obtained by successive grades
 7 of purification. The mean hydrodynamic diameter ($\langle 2R_H \rangle$) of the particles increased with
 8 each purification step, starting from $\langle 2R_H \rangle = 6 \pm 3$ nm (Au@RITC_{1a}), $\langle 2R_H \rangle = 10 \pm 3$ nm
 9 (Au@RITC_{1b}), up to $\langle 2R_H \rangle = 40 \pm 8$ nm – 200 ± 15 (Au@RITC_{1c}), showing peak
 10 enlargement and increased dispersity, due to coalescence phenomena (see Fig. 2b). The
 11 surface charge of the NPs was investigated by means of ζ potential measurements. After
 12 the first step of purification (Au@RITC_{1a}) the ζ potential measurement shows evidence of
 13 an unstable colloidal system (ζ potential = -16 ± 3 mV reported in Supporting Information
 14 Fig. S1a), mainly due to the presence of residual unreacted chemicals. After the next
 15 purification step (Au@RITC_{1b}), the ζ potential value became -28 ± 3 mV (see Supporting
 16 Information Fig. S1b), showing an almost stable colloidal system, with negative charge on
 17 the surface of the Au@RITC NPs.

1

2 **Fig. 2** DLS measurements on Au@RITC NPs: a) Mean hydrodynamic diameter ($\langle 2R_H \rangle$) = $10 \pm$
 3 3 nm for Au@RITC_1 with molar ratio 1/1 in pink and $\langle 2R_H \rangle = 50 \pm 20 - 500 \pm 30$ nm for
 4 Au@RITC_2 with molar ratio 1/0.1 in black; b) size of Au@RITC_1 at different purification
 5 steps: in violet $\langle 2R_H \rangle_{\text{Au@RITC}_{1a}} = 6 \pm 3$ nm; in pink $\langle 2R_H \rangle_{\text{Au@RITC}_{1b}} = 10 \pm 3$ nm; in blue
 6 $\langle 2R_H \rangle_{\text{Au@RITC}_{1c}} = 40 \pm 8 - 200 \pm 15$ nm.

7

8 The FESEM investigation of Au@RITC_1b, shown in Fig. 3, revealed spherically shaped
 9 particles, monodispersed and with diameters of 10 nm, in good agreement with DLS data.

10

11

12

13

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Fig. 3 FESEM image of Au@RITC_1b NPs showing sizes around 10 nm.

In order to characterize the chemical structure of the products FTIR, NMR and XPS studies were carried out on Au@RITC and the pure RITC sample for comparison. The Au@RITC_1b sample was employed for this purpose as it is considered to be the best sample in terms of stability and dispersity.

FTIR spectra confirmed the RITC presence on the metal surface (see FTIR spectra of RITC and Au@RITC_1b in Supporting Information Fig. S2): the band at 1717 cm^{-1} , due to C=O stretching of carboxylic acid group, and the band at 1395 cm^{-1} , attributable to CH_2 bending of $-\text{N}-(\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3)_2$ groups, were observed. The band at 1495 cm^{-1} due to the C-N stretching in the isothiocyanate⁴³ was shifted to 1487 cm^{-1} . Furthermore, both the band at 2125 cm^{-1} (attributed to the isothiocyanate group) and the doublet $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ at 880 cm^{-1} disappeared. This suggests the involvement of the $-\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S}$ moiety in the binding, as reported in the literature for analogous systems, and that the concentration of free dye is low.^{44,45,46}

In the ^1H NMR experiments on pure RITC (spectrum reported in Fig. 4a) sharp and well resolved resonances of the aromatic protons (6.8-7.4 ppm) as well as of the ethyl group protons (1.05 and 3.5 ppm) can be observed. In comparison, the ^1H NMR spectrum of

1 Au@RITC_1b (Fig. 4b) shows the presence of both sharp and broad resonances of aromatic
2 and aliphatic protons. This can be attributed to the presence of both RITC bound to the
3 nanoparticle, which gives rise to broad signals due to reduced mobility, and physisorbed
4 RITC, which is characterized by greater mobility and thus sharper resonances.⁴⁷
5 Furthermore, the relative intensities in the peaks indicate a larger concentration of bound
6 RITC with respect to physisorbed RITC. Moreover, a resonance at 7.74 ppm, present in
7 Au@RITC_1b but absent in the spectrum of native RITC, is observed. This new resonance,
8 which belongs to the protons of the aromatic ring bearing the isothiocyanate moiety, can
9 be attributed to the binding of the RITC on the nanoparticle. At the same time, no major
10 variation of the chemical shift of the ethyl moieties can be observed, and therefore it is
11 possible to hypothesize that the binding of RITC on the nanoparticle occurs mainly
12 involving the isothiocyanate group.

13 Another confirmation of the bond between RITC and the AuNPs can be observed in the
14 Au@RITC_1b Nuclear Overhauser Effect Spectroscopy (NOESY) spectrum (Fig. 4c). NOESY
15 experiment shows cross peaks between protons whose distance remains constant during
16 the observation time (about 200 ms). The presence of correlations between the $-CH_3$ (1.09
17 ppm) and $-CH_2-$ (3.26 ppm) protons of the ethyl groups, commonly absent in small
18 molecules, indicates that these moieties are characterized by low rotational mobility.
19 Moreover, there are large correlations near the diagonal peaks in the region between 6
20 and 8 ppm, where the protons of the aromatic moieties resonate. The entity of these cross
21 peaks suggests that, compared to molecules free to rotate in the solvent, the aromatic
22 rings have an even greater reduction of rotational mobility than the ethyl groups. This
23 suggests that the aromatic rings, in particular the one bearing the isothiocyanate group,
24 are close to the NP surface.

1

2 **Fig. 4** NMR spectra of Au@RITC and RITC: a) ¹H spectrum of pure RITC; b) ¹H spectrum of
 3 Au@RITC_1b; c) NOESY spectrum of Au@RITC_1b.

4

5 High resolution synchrotron radiation-induced XPS measurements were performed on the
 6 Au@RITC_1b sample with the aim of obtaining a better insight into the dye molecular structure
 7 stability upon conjugation to the surface of the NPs; furthermore, the accurate analysis of

1 Au@RITC_1b electronic structure gave interesting information about the dye-metal interaction.
2 Measurements were performed on the C1s, S2p, N1s, O1s and Au4f core levels. All binding energy
3 (BE) values, FWHM and atomic ratios are reported in Supporting Information Table S2.
4 The measured C1s core level spectrum confirms the stability of the RITC molecular structure. C1s
5 signal appears composite, and by applying a peak-fitting procedure at least five components can
6 be identified (reported in Supporting Information Fig. S3), corresponding respectively to C
7 atoms bonded to other carbons in aromatic molecules (aromatic C-C) and aliphatic C atoms in -CH₃
8 moieties (aliphatic C-C) (C1: 284.7 eV), C atoms bonded to N in C-N and -NCS groups (C2: 286.0
9 eV), C-O-C carbons (C3: 287 eV), C atoms of the C=N⁺ moiety (C4: nearly 288 eV) and, at higher BE
10 values, C atoms of the carboxyl group (C5: about 288.8 eV). It is noteworthy that C1 contribution,
11 attributed to both aromatic and aliphatic C-C, is centered at the BE reported in the literature for
12 aromatic C atoms because the contribution from aliphatic C atoms of CH₃ moieties is very small (4
13 aliphatic over 14 aromatic C atoms).

14 The experimental atomic ratio between the five C1s spectral components is C1:C2:C3:C4:C5 = 20.5:
15 8.4: 2.0: 1.6: 1, and is in excellent agreement with the C1:C2:C3:C4:C5 = 18.0: 7.0: 2.0: 1.0: 1
16 atomic ratio expected from the molecular structure (C1 = 14 aromatic + 4 aliphatic).

17 S2p, N1s and Au4f signals provide useful information about the interaction between the dye
18 molecule and the metallic NPs. As for the metal NPs, the Au4f spectrum, shown in Fig. 5a, consists
19 of two pairs of spin-orbit components. The first feature (Au4f_{7/2} BE = 83.97 eV) is associated with
20 metallic gold, and is due to gold atoms in the bulk of the nanoparticles; the spin-orbit pair of
21 lower intensity at higher BE values (Au4f_{7/2} BE = 84.66 eV) is indicative of positively charged metal
22 atoms, as expected for surface atoms interacting with a capping molecule.^{48,49,50}

1 The S2p and N1s spectra provide interesting information leading to the hypothesis that an
2 electronic interaction occurs between the SCN moiety and the gold atoms at the NP surface. As
3 shown in Fig. 5b, the S2p spectrum shows two pairs of spin-orbit components; the first doublet
4 (S2p_{3/2} BE = 161.59 eV) arises at BE values typical of sulfur atoms covalently bonded to carbon in
5 isothiocyanate (SCN-R) moieties,^{51,52} the second signal, at higher BE values (S2p_{3/2} BE = 164.13 eV)
6 is compatible with literature data reported for isothiocyanate moieties undergoing interactions
7 with metals through the S atom.⁵²

8 As for N1s signal (Fig. 5c), a main peak is observed at 397.5 eV BE (N1), as expected for N atoms in
9 SCN-R and amine-like groups;⁵¹ a spectral component of lower intensity, attributed to the
10 charged imine-like nitrogen, arises at higher BE (N2: 398.4 eV).

11 Furthermore, the experimental atomic ratio N1:N2 = 1.9 : 1.0 is in very good agreement with the
12 RITC molecular structure (expected atomic ratio N1 : N2 = 2.0 : 1.0).

13

1

2 **Fig. 5** HR-XPS spectra collected at a) Au4f, b) S2p, and c) N1s core levels for the
 3 Au@RITC_1b sample.

4

5 3.2 Experimental and simulated UV-Vis extinction spectra of Au@RITC NPs

6 The experimental UV-Vis extinction spectra of Au@RITC_1a, Au@RITC_1b and
 7 Au@RITC_1c samples were examined and compared.

8 Fig. 6 reports the three spectra in the wavelength range 400-800 nm in different colours,
 9 together with the extinction spectrum of RITC (5×10^{-5} M in water solution). The spectrum of

1 the pure dye is dominated by the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ electronic transition, centred at 552 nm with a
2 shoulder around 520 nm, attributable to a vibronic transition.

3 Au@RITC_1a presents a broad structured band with a maximum at 565 nm and a shoulder
4 around 535 nm. This spectral feature is due to the superimposition of the spectral
5 extinction of the dye and the gold SPR, which cannot be resolved by static absorption
6 spectroscopy. After the next step of purification, we observe for Au@RITC_1b two broad
7 features at 558 nm and 612 nm. This latter absorption is attributed to the extended
8 SPR.^{53,54} In Au@RITC_1c, the strong cleavage induces a depletion of the capping agent, and
9 strong coalescence phenomena occur: in this case the experimental evidence in the UV-Vis
10 spectrum is a very broad peak at 569 nm, and a high baseline due to the presence of light
11 scattering by large NPs, as confirmed by FESEM (data not shown). The Au@RITC_1c sample
12 will not be taken into account in the following analysis as it does not provide any useful
13 information about the plasmonic response of the particle-particle aggregates.

21

22 **Fig. 6** UV-Vis extinction spectra of RITC (green line), Au@RITC_1a (blue line), Au@RITC_1b
23 (black line) and Au@RITC_1c (violet line). The spectra have been offset and rescaled to
24 make them comparable.

1 In order to discriminate between the contributions of RITC and plasmonic resonances to
2 the UV-Vis spectra of Au@RITC, theoretical simulations have been conducted.
3 Fig. 7 reports the comparison between the experimental (black line) and predicted (grey
4 line) UV-Vis extinction spectra of Au@RITC_1a and Au@RITC_1b. The colored dashed lines
5 represent the predicted spectra for all the separate contributions to the overall absorption
6 of Au@RITC.

7 The models for the simulation of the UV-Vis spectra are based on the chemical and physical
8 analysis described in the previous section. Firstly, the FESEM images (an example image is
9 reported in Fig. 3) indicate that the average NP diameter is around 10 nm.

10 From the NMR/FTIR/XPS analyses it was deduced that the RITC is bonded to the AuNPs via
11 the S atom of the isothiocyanate group, that other parts of the molecule are less perturbed
12 and that the molecule is rotationally rigid. We therefore assume that the RITC molecule is
13 rigidly upright with the isothiocyanate moiety toward the NP.

14 This gives two possible interparticle geometries: end to end interaction of the RITC
15 molecules bonded to separate NPs would lead to an interparticle gap of approx. 2 nm due
16 to the approx. 1 nm length of the RITC molecule; overlaying interaction between RITC
17 molecules would give approx. 1 nm gap.

18 The simulations of the UV-Vis extinction spectra (data not shown) show that a 2 nm gap
19 cannot explain the experimental spectrum as the interaction between NPs is too weak, we
20 have therefore chosen the 1 nm gap geometry. The simulations required calculation of the
21 extinction coefficient of the system in two geometries: the transverse plasmon geometry in
22 which the direction of propagation of the light is perpendicular to the interaxis of the NP
23 chain and the linear polarization is also orthogonal to this axis; the extended plasmon

1 geometry which has the same propagation axis of the light but the polarization is parallel
2 to the interaxis of the NP chain.

3

4

5 **Fig. 7** Experimental (black line) and simulated (grey line) UV-Vis extinction spectra of a)
6 Au@RITC_1a and b) Au@RITC_1b. The colored dashed lines represent the simulated
7 spectra for the separate contributions coming from the RITC dye molecules (green), and
8 the transverse (blue) and extended plasmon (red) resonances of the NP aggregates.
9 Schematic representation of the transverse and extended plasmon geometries are also
10 reported.

11

1 To simulate the effect of nanoparticles aggregation in solution, the calculations were
2 repeated for chains of different lengths (1, 2, 4, 6 and infinite NPs). This choice was
3 imposed by the experimental geometry in which the linear polarization of the light means
4 that only the linear segments aligned with the polarization of the pump were excited, even
5 though the sample may contain complex and extended 3D aggregates.

6 Furthermore, two models were considered to simulate differing quantities of RITC on the
7 surface of the NPs: 10 nm NPs spaced by 1 nm in which a 0.5 nm 'layer' of RITC covers each
8 particle and the ensemble is embedded in water to simulate the case in which the surface
9 of the NPs is completely covered by RITC (model A); the same model without the layer of
10 RITC to simulate the case in which so few RITC molecules are bound to the surface that the
11 plasmonic effect is conditioned by the dielectric constant of the water in which the NPs are
12 immersed (model B).

13 The extinction spectra for the transverse and extended plasmon geometries and for both
14 models, as well as for each chain length, are shown in Supporting Information Fig. S4.

15 One can see from these simulations that the extended plasmon is shifted to longer
16 wavelengths, the longer the chain of NPs. There is relatively little difference between the
17 wavelength of maximum intensity of the extinction spectra of 6 NPs and infinite NPs (in the
18 case of the extended plasmon in model B the difference is 30 nm but the shift is rapidly
19 converging).

20 On the other hand, the transverse plasmon is shifted to lower wavelengths with respect to
21 the isolated particle, albeit by a much smaller amount than the extended plasmon shift.

22 Such observations are consistent with what has been observed in the literature.⁵⁵

1 We limit the contributions of the 'infinite' NP array to the simulated spectra because even
2 in the case of long chains their curvature means that only a limited number of particles in
3 the chain can be aligned with the polarization of the incoming light.

4 The position of the extended plasmon in the UV-Vis spectrum of the Au@RITC_1a sample is
5 well reproduced by the simulated extinction spectrum of the extended plasmon resonance
6 of model A, while the equivalent spectrum of model B matches quite well to the extended
7 plasmon frequency of the Au@RITC_1b sample.

8 With this in mind we simulated the experimental UV-Vis spectra of Au@RITC_1a with a flat
9 distribution of chains (*i.e.* chains of length 1, 2, 4, 6 and infinite NPs equally probable) and
10 model A (see Fig. 7a), while that of the Au@RITC_1b sample was simulated by the same
11 combination of chains but with model B (see Fig. 7b). Furthermore, a contribution of the
12 RITC extinction spectra is added to the resulting sum of extended and transverse
13 geometries to minimise the difference between the simulated and experimental spectra
14 although the agreement between experiment and simulation is not very sensitive to the
15 precise quantity of RITC.

16 These comparisons are shown in Fig. 7 where the contributions of the transverse and
17 extended plasmon geometries (summed over the different chain lengths) and free RITC to
18 the simulated spectra are shown as dashed lines.

19 The first point to note from Fig. 7 is that the main features of the experimental spectra are
20 reproduced in the simulations. This would appear to validate the assumptions made in the
21 modelling. The main region where there is disagreement is in the spectral range $> 650\text{nm}$.

22 In this region it may be possible that there are contributions to the experimental spectra
23 due to 2D aggregates and/or NP chains with interparticle spacing of $< 1\text{ nm}$ which are not
24 accounted for in the simulation. Nonetheless, as the maxima of the extended spectra are

1 well reproduced in both cases by the simulation we conclude that the shift of the
2 frequency of maximum intensity of the extended plasmon from 566 nm in the case of
3 Au@RITC_1a to 612 nm in the case of sample Au@RITC_1b is mainly due to a reduction of
4 the quantity of RITC on the surface of the NPs.

5 Therefore, by modulating the amount of dielectric material between the NPs (by the
6 number of washing cycles of the final product) it is possible to control the frequency of the
7 extended plasmon resonance and visibly change the colour of the final solution.

8

9 *3.3 Transient spectroscopy of Au@RITC NPs*

10 To confirm these theoretical predictions and discriminate between the different
11 contributions to the plasmonic response of the Au@RITC_1a and Au@RITC_1b samples, we
12 have followed their ultrafast relaxation dynamics after irradiation with a pump beam at
13 400 nm, which causes excitation of both the NPs in the gold interband transition and the
14 free RITC.

15 Fig. 8 reports the Transient Absorbance (TA) spectra in the range 425-750 nm for the
16 Au@RITC_1a and Au@RITC_1b samples. The spectra are shown at selected pump-probe
17 delays in the range 0.5 - 10 ps. For comparison, the transient absorbance spectrum of pure
18 RITC dye (5×10^{-5} M in water solution) is also reported, in the same range of wavelengths.

19 The TA spectrum of RITC is dominated by an intense negative feature centred at 558 nm
20 with a shoulder around 535 nm, and a lower positive band with a maximum around 444 nm
21 (red continuous arrow in Fig. 8a). The former signals can be ascribed mainly to stimulated
22 emission from the excited S_1 state of the dye with possible contributions from ground state
23 bleaching. The positive signal, which is photoinduced absorption, can be assigned to
24 absorption of the S_1 excited state (excited state absorption).

1 The temporal evolution of RITC absorbance spectra is characterized by different
2 contributions with different time-scales. The quick decay in the first few picoseconds can
3 be attributed to collisional quenching with the solvent molecules,⁵⁶ while the longer time
4 constant of the order of a few nanoseconds is due to the typical fluorescence decay of the
5 dye solution. The intermediate lifetime, in the range of tens of picoseconds, can be related
6 to the presence of dye aggregates,⁵⁷ whose formation has to be considered in a $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$
7 water solution.⁵⁸ As indicated by the black dotted arrow, the wavelength position of the
8 band does not show significant time dependence.

9 Two negative features are clearly visible in the TA spectra of Au@RITC_1a and
10 Au@RITC_1b: one centred around 532 nm for both solutions and a more intense feature at
11 585 nm or at 630 nm, respectively for Au@RITC_1a and Au@RITC_1b. These features can
12 be attributed to the bleaching of the transverse and extended SPR, and, as expected, their
13 temporal evolution shows an intense and rapid decrease of the signal in the first five
14 picoseconds, due to electron-phonon coupling.⁵⁹

15 As generally found, two positive wings on both sides of the strong bleaching signals are
16 present, the one on the blue side being much more intense.⁶⁰

17 The bandwidth of the extended SPR bleaching appears to be larger for Au@RITC_1b and its
18 position is shifted towards higher wavelength with respect to Au@RITC_1a in agreement
19 with what is found in the corresponding static extinction spectra.

20 A displacement of the position of the extended SPR is also observed at the different delay
21 times, as indicated by the black dotted arrows in the TA spectra: in the first ten
22 picoseconds, the band maximum shifts towards the blue by about ten nanometers. As the
23 band is a convolution of the extended SPR bleachings coming from aggregates of different
24 lengths (see Supporting Information Fig. S4 for the simulations), it can be inferred that they

1 also have a different time dependence, *i.e.* that longer chains have a shorter lifetime than
2 shorter chains.⁶¹ After the initial rapid decrease of the signal, the TA spectra evolve with a
3 slower recovery to zero, but the intensity ratio of the long and short time scale
4 contributions appears to be different in samples Au@RITC_1a and Au@RITC_1b.

5

6

7 **Fig. 8** TA spectra of (a) pure RITC, $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$ water solution, (b) Au@RITC_1a, (c)
8 Au@RITC_1b. The spectra are acquired at different time delays following 400 nm
9 excitation, *i.e.* 0.5 ps, 1 ps, 2.5 ps, 5 ps, 7.5 ps and 10 ps.

10

11 Comparing the residual signal in Fig. 8b and 8c after the first ten picoseconds, it can be
12 seen that about 50% of the Au@RITC_1a signal remains, while it is almost completely
13 depleted in Au@RITC_1b. To explain this difference in the dynamics, we have to consider
14 that the long-time decay can be attributed to nanoparticle heat dissipation processes with

1 the environment (phonon-phonon coupling),⁶² as well as to the long timescale fluorescence
2 of RITC. These slow contributions are difficult to distinguish as they overlap in the same
3 wavelength range.

4 In order to discriminate between these effects we have investigated the photoinduced
5 absorption present in the spectra of both dye and Au@RITC below 500 nm: as described,
6 RITC presents a positive signal around 444 nm (red continuous arrow in Fig. 8a), while the
7 bleaching of the plasmon resonance is associated with a strong positive wing around 460-
8 470 nm (black continuous arrows in Fig. 8b and 8c). In the TA spectrum of Au@RITC_1a
9 both of these features are present and can be distinguished by the different position of the
10 maxima and by the temporal evolution, as the plasmonic component of the band (black
11 continuous arrow in Fig. 8b) decays faster than the dye component (red continuous arrow
12 in Fig. 8b). In the TA spectrum of Au@RITC_1b we observe prevalently the plasmonic
13 component of the band (black continuous arrow in Fig. 8c).

14 Thus, it can be argued that Au@RITC_1b ultrafast transient absorbance is dominated by
15 plasmonic dynamics and its long scale evolution can be principally attributed to phonon-
16 phonon relaxation processes. In the case of Au@RITC_1a, a significant contribution from
17 RITC can be observed and thus the slow decay can be associated with both phonon-phonon
18 coupling and dye fluorescence. This gives support to the models proposed for the
19 simulation of the static spectra of these samples presented in the previous section.

20

21 **4. Conclusions**

22 Gold nanoparticles functionalized by rhodamine B isothiocyanate were synthesized and
23 investigated in order to elucidate their chemical and physical properties while modulating
24 the dye/Au molar ratios during the synthesis. For the ratio Au:RITC = 1:1 (mol/mol)

1 together with intermediate washing in deionized water we obtained the Au@RITC_1b
2 sample, with monodispersed nanoparticles of 10 ± 3 nm, as shown by DLS measurements
3 and confirmed by FESEM. The NMR and XPS analysis performed on this sample provides
4 evidence that the dye molecules are rotationally rigid and that the binding occurs mainly
5 through the isothiocyanate group of dye.

6 The static UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy performed on Au@RITC showed the presence of
7 a broad and structured absorption feature, coming from the superimposed spectral
8 contributions of the dye and both transverse and extended gold NP plasmon resonances.
9 The latter two are due to the hybridization of the plasmon resonances of closely spaced
10 nanoparticles in the aggregate. We observed that the plasmonic response of these
11 nanoparticle aggregate assemblies is controlled by the amount of rhodamine B
12 isothiocyanate around the gold core of the nanoparticle.

13 Theoretical simulations of the static extinction spectra of Au@RITC with different steps of
14 purification were conducted in order to aid the interpretation of the experimental data and
15 transient absorption spectroscopy measurements were performed in order to temporally
16 and energetically discriminate and investigate the spectral contributions from RITC and
17 plasmon resonances.

18 Both simulation and experiments point to a strong correlation between the position of the
19 extended plasmon resonance and the concentration of RITC molecules on the nanoparticle
20 surface. In particular, increasing the purification of Au@RITC we have found a red-shift of
21 the extended plasmon resonance: the maximum of the band shifts from 558 nm to 612 nm,
22 with the band broadening up to 700 nm. Accordingly, modulating the amount of capping
23 agent, and in turn the dielectric constant of the material between the nanoparticles, it is
24 possible to tune the plasmon resonance of the Au@RITC assembly over a large range of

1 wavelengths. The detailed inspection of the positive and negative bands in the transient
2 absorbance spectra of two Au@RITC samples has allowed us to distinguish between the
3 contributions of dye fluorescence and nanoparticle SPR, illustrating the disappearance of
4 RITC fluorescence in the spectrum of highly purified Au@RITC. Such control over the
5 plasmonic response of these materials is the first step to the exploitation of aggregates *via*
6 plasmonic excitation for processes such as nanofabrication (melting) (e.g. reference 5) and
7 nanoscale controlled thermal deposition.⁶³

8

9 **Conflict of Interest.** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

10

11 **Author Contributions** I.F., A.C., and I.V. designed and made the chemical experimental
12 synthesis and performed the FTIR and DLS measurements and evaluations. G.T. and F.S.
13 performed the NMR measurements and the data analysis. L.C. and C.B. performed the XPS
14 measurements and the data analysis. E. M. and I. P. provided technical support in SR-XPS
15 measurements. D.C., P.O'K., A.P., F.T., S.T., and L.A. performed the UV-Vis and pump-probe
16 measurements and the data analysis. R.P.Z performed the simulations of the UV-Vis
17 extinction spectra of the Au@RITC NP aggregates. All authors contributed to the paper
18 writing.

19

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24

1 **Appendix A. Supplementary material**

2 Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version.

3

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